

Tree-planting has enormous potential but significant socio-ecological challenges for climate action

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Planting of trees, even forests, doesn't guarantee a reduction in total emissions as nations strive to meet hard targets.

Tree-planting features prominently on discourses around climate change mitigation and possible strategies. These initiatives are quick to capture public imagination because of its apparent ease and promise of long-term benefits. Such campaigns have truly gone global.

For example, Goal 5 of the **New York Declaration on Forests**, a voluntary and non-binding political declaration involving civil society and some local governments targets the restoration of 150 million hectares of degraded landscapes and forestlands by 2020 and an additional 200 million hectares by 2030. It is widely and well-understood that planting trees, under the broader umbrella of restoring natural ecosystems, remains among a bouquet of climate actions that need our attention — and urgently.